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Optimization and machine learning applied to last-mile logistics: a review

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Abstract: The growth in e-commerce that our society is facing in the last years is changing the view companies have on last-mile logistics, due to its increasing impact on the whole supply chain. New technologies are raising users' expectations, with the need to develop customized delivery experiences; moreover, increasing pressure on supply-chains also create additional challenges for suppliers. At the same time this phenomenon generates an increase in the impacts on the liveability of our cities, due to traffic congestion, occupation of public spaces and environmental and acoustic pollution linked to urban logistics. In this context the optimization of last-mile deliveries is an imperative for companies with parcels that need to be delivered in the urban areas, but also for public administrations that want to guarantee a good quality of life for citizens. In recent years, many scholars have focused on the study of logistics optimization techniques and in particular of the last-mile. In addition to traditional optimization techniques, linked to the disciplines of operations research, the recent advances in the use of sensors and IoT, and the consequent large amount of data that derives from it, are pushing towards a greater use of big data and analytics techniques - such as machine learning and artificial intelligence - also in this sector. Based on this premise, the aim of this work is to provide an overview on the most recent literature advance related to last-mile deliveries optimization techniques, to be used as a baseline for scholars who intend to explore new approaches and techniques in the study of last-mile logistics optimization. A bibliometric analysis and a critical review were conducted in order to highlight the main studied problems, the algorithms used and the case study. Results from the analysis allows to cluster the studies in traditional optimization models, machine learning approaches and mixed methods. Main research gaps and limitations of the current literature are assessed, in order to identify unaddressed challenges and provide research suggestions for future approaches.

Keywords: keyword 1; keyword 2; keyword 3 (List three to ten pertinent keywords specific to the article yet reasonably common within the subject discipline.)

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1. Introduction

Last-mile logistics is a phenomenon steadily increasing, mainly due to the ongoing urbanization and changes in consumers' habits, with the strong growth in online retailing and the consequent increase in e-groceries and e-commerce activities. Last figures show that in the EU the share of online shoppers equalled 64% of all individuals aged 16-74 [1]. This growing pressure of freight traffic in urban areas brings with it a series of externalities that undermine the sustainability and liveability of our cities. It increases congestion and emissions in urban areas, due to the additional traffic generated by vehicles for

deliveries that often have overlapping routes (25% of CO₂, and 30 to 50% of PM and NO_x); moreover, it reduces road safety due to the presence of heavy vehicles [2]. The restriction measures associated to COVID-19 pandemic further accelerated the increase in online purchasing, while being a “rare catalyst” for logistic innovations [3]. However, notwithstanding the recent efforts done to improve the sustainability of logistics, issues related to the whole process are still debated. New technologies can play a key role in improving the impact of last-mile deliveries in urban areas. Aside from the already well-known smart technologies associated with online purchasing, the entire logistics supply chain can also take advantage of innovative processes, being a fertile ground for automation. More in detail, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) approaches have become a hot topic in literature and practice, and they are interfacing more and more with the traditional Vehicle Routing Optimization (VRO) models present in the literature; their algorithms are in fact able to give exact predictions - based on historic data - to efficiency problems common to supply chains, e.g. demand forecasting, routing and tracking, while being able to detect anomalies during the process [4]. These algorithms are constantly evolving, and, thanks to recent disruptions, the last few years have been crucial for this research field and its development.

Based on these premises, this study presents an overview on the most recent literature advance on last-mile logistics optimization techniques, starting from the results of the SENATOR project¹ whose aim is to produce governance schemes on user demand planning, transport planning, freight and logistics planning and city infrastructure. The overview includes a bibliometric analysis and a critical review of the main studies and results presented by scholars on the subject, considering traditional VRO models, ML models and mixed approaches. The studies were therefore classified according to the problem considered, the methodology adopted, and the case study and the main research gaps and limitations were assessed. The final aim is to provide an overview on the topic to be considered as a baseline for scholars who intend to explore new topics in the study of last-mile logistics optimization.

The remainder of the paper is organized as follows. Section 2 describes the methodology adopted for the selection of the studies and their clustering. Section 3 presents the results of the analysis, both in terms of critical review and bibliometric analysis, and describes current limitations and gaps in the state of the art. Finally, section 4 draws the conclusions.

2. Methodology

The methodology is based on the following steps: (i) selection of scientific studies and clustering; (ii) bibliometric analysis; (iii) critical review; (iv) discussion.

For the purpose of this work, the selection of the studies has been conducted considering only papers published and indexed in the Scopus database. The papers have been selected from the document “State of the art in optimization and machine learning algorithms applied to last-mile logistics” [5] developed in the SENATOR project. This analysis was published in June 2021, so papers published after that date are not included in the analysis. A classification of the resulting papers has been conducted using the VOSviewer software. VOSviewer is a software tool for constructing and visualizing bibliometric networks, offering text mining functionality that can be used to construct and visualize networks of words extracted from a body of scientific literature [6]. The software allows to perform a co-occurrence analysis and this feature was used to cluster the reviewed studies in different groups according to the main keywords indicated by the authors.

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The software VOSviewer has then been used for a deeper bibliometric analysis of the studies, considering citations for each document, in order to identify papers which might be considered as cornerstones, and analysing co-authorship and authors' scientometrics, to highlight the role of main scholars and experts in the field. A critical review has then been conducted on the topic dealt in the selected papers, in order to analyse the main problems studies, the methods applied, the case studies and the efficiency of the proposed approaches. The following section describes in detail the result of the performed analyses.

3. Results

3.1. Selection of papers

A total of 77 papers resulted from the selection procedure. Of the 77 papers analysed, 17 are review paper, while the others are research articles. The temporal analysis in Figure 1 shows that the literature on the subject began to flourish in the early 2000s and has been growing in recent years; this is in line with the trend of city logistics.

Figure 1. Temporal analysis of publications (Own elaboration).

3.2. Papers clustering

The bibliometric network of the selected paper has then been analysed through VOSviewer. The software is able to use as input a Scopus list of papers, exported in csv format. Its algorithm performs word mining of the keywords included by the authors and automatically assigned by the indexing database, with a procedure called "co-occurrence". For a first analysis we decided to include as unit only authors' keywords and set the minimum number of occurrences of a keyword to 5. Of the 240 keywords, only 5 meet this threshold. The 5 resulting words are city logistics, routing, vehicle routing, vehicle routing problem and machine learning. In order to create a keyword network, the software computes for each keyword the total link strength, i.e. the number of publications in which two keywords occur together. Results of the co-occurrence analysis are reported in Table 1.

Table 1. Keywords co-occurrence analysis (Own elaboration from VOSwiever software results).

Keyword	Occurrences	Total Link Strength
City logistics	5	3
Routing	5	2
Vehicle Routing Problem	14	2
Machine Learning	7	1
Vehicle Routing	10	0

Results of the co-occurrence analysis allows to perform some considerations:

- The item *vehicle routing* has a total link strength equal to 0; this is probably due to the presence of the full *vehicle routing problem* keyword.
- For the purposes of our analysis 3 of the 5 keywords may be considered as synonyms, namely *vehicle routing problem*, *vehicle routing*, *routing*.
- This leads us to consider that the 3 main keywords can be considered: *city logistics*, *machine learning* and *vehicle routing problem*.

Table 3. Citation analysis (Own elaboration from VOSviewer software results).

Rank	Author	Document	Citations
1	Semet F.	3	486
2	Cattaruzza D.	3	191
3	Zhang Z.	3	78
4	Gendreau M	2	797
5	Absi N.	2	174
6	Feillet D.	2	174
7	Vidal T.	2	172
8	Wang J.	2	111
9	Zhou Y.	2	111
10	Demir E.	2	98

Figure 3. Co-authorship network (Source: VOSviewer)

In the following, a critical review of the selected papers, according to the three clusters is proposed.

3.3. Critical review

3.3.1. Machine Learning models

ML algorithms find several research applications in logistics; the main topics that are drawn from the literature analysis are: warehouse issues, the predictions of traffic flows and demand, supply chain process, customer satisfaction.

Self-learning ML techniques are common in the case of the Warehouse cluster. The algorithms are used to read handwritten documents and to detect frequent events. In this respect, Guermazi et al. [7] propose an entity-matching approach to validate logistics entities by matching names and addresses, using Word Embedding and Supervised Learning techniques, with good accuracy results. More recently Bricher and Müller [8] trained deep neural networks to fully automate the control process for container logistics, allowing operators to add new container types with automatically labelled images from the observed container routing workflow. Wojtusiak et al. [9] apply the Inferential Theory of Learning in multiagent-based simulation environments in the case of autonomous logistics to predict future traffic flows, showing that agents with learning abilities are more efficient than inexperienced agents in their tasks.

One of the most spreading applications of ML in logistics is the one related to the forecasting of demand trends. This is important and needed both for manufacturers (to predict production levels, e.g. [10]), transport operators (for vehicle capacity optimization) and retailers (to plan their stock), reducing risks at an early stage of the supply chain. In 2009 Gao and Feng [11] developed a model based on Support Vector Machine regression with a self-adaptive parameter-adjust iterative algorithm, enhancing the convergence rate and the forecasting accuracy. More recently Hess et al. [12] tested both classical forecasting

and machine learning methods adapting the models to the typical demand (intermittent with a double-seasonal pattern). The results from the case study with a limited demand history (less than 2 months), machine learning performs better than traditional methods. Albadrani et al. [13] explored the use of K-nearest neighbours together with Random Forests (RF) and Support Vector Machine (SVM) to support inbound logistics planning. Another recent work is the one by Lickert et al. [14], who proposed a set of criteria to compare supervised learning algorithms for classification tasks in Reverse Logistics.

Another debated issue is the one of customer satisfaction. Tamayo et al. [15] used social media content to test the public perception of city logistics using Unsupervised Learning and Natural Language Processing, to perform content and sentiment analysis. Results showed that the overall view of city logistics is more positive than negative. Tian et al. [16] propose a blockchain-based evaluation approach, using Long Short-Term Memory algorithm, with four criteria affecting customer satisfaction in urban logistics: cargo damages rate; on-time delivery rate; cost performance; information transparency.

Several studies address the topic of Anomaly Detection (AD) in logistics. Rosen & Medvedev [17] developed an algorithm for AD in vehicles' trajectories and proved its effectiveness with an application on a real data set containing trajectories of cargo vessels. Feng & Timmermans [18] dealt with the use of three ML algorithms (Bayesian belief network, Decision Tree and Random Forest) to analyse anomalies in GPS traces. In 2018 Sarikan & Ozbayoglu [19] applied k-nearest neighbour algorithm for unsupervised learning and image processing to detect vehicular flow directions; the method proved to be reliable in the case of a single lane road. Recently, Savic et al. [20] embeds autoencoder based AD modules into the 3GPP mobile cellular IoT architecture; they custom-designed a novel NB-IoT device platform for a Smart Logistics case study, where NB-IoT devices are connected to shipping containers in a factory supply chain, to collect data, deploy and test the modules, with successful AD results.

A growing demand leads to a growing request of spaces for urban logistics; a solution is the locating of consolidation centres outside the urban area to ensure the readiness of the delivery while reducing the impact of heavy vehicles presence inside the city. El Ouadi et al. [21] developed a ML algorithm for the dimensioning of the centre, considering proximity and logistics demand behaviour; they applied the algorithm to experimental data showing its usefulness.

The topic of safety and security has been addressed using ML algorithms by Zhao et al. [22], who used generalized regression neural network (GRNN) combined with particle swarm optimization (PSO) to predict accidents, and the a priori algorithm to analyse the combination of high-frequency risk factors in the whole process, including pick up, warehouse storage, transport, and the end distribution.

ML algorithms can play a key role when it comes to innovative technological solutions. In their study Marcucci et al. [23] discussed the Digital Twin concept, suggesting the joint use of behavioural and simulation models within a Living Lab approach so as to stimulate effective, well-informed and participated planning processes, but also to forecast both behaviour and reactions to structural changes and policy measures implementations. The use of electric vehicles has been investigated by Kretzschmar et al. [24] using a ML based range prediction model including routing, traffic and weather data able to reproduce consumption levels (with an error below the 10%). Another explanatory example is the study of Sindhwani et al. [25], proposing an anomaly detection framework for a fleet of drones to perform parcel pickup and delivery tasks. The unsupervised algorithm can fit predictive flight dynamics models while identifying and discarding abnormal flight missions from the training set, outperforming alternative robust detection methods on synthetic benchmark problems.

3.3.2. Vehicle Routing Optimization models

Optimization models have long been used in operational research and consequently in logistics in the The Travelling Salesman Problem (TSP) and the Vehicle Routing

Problem (VRP) [26]. The objective of the TSP is to find a route that, starting and ending at the same point, visits once every node minimizing the total cost of the trip [27]. In addition, in the VRP the total demand of customers visited on a route should not exceed the capacity of the vehicle that performs it. Both problems are combinatorial optimization and NP-hard problems, whose optimal solution becomes computationally intractable to obtain, once the size of the graph increases [28; 29].

More recently, several variants of the VRP have been studied. A first class of variants is the one of the Rich Vehicle Routing Problems (RVRP) [30], which deal with realistic optimization functions, uncertainty, dynamism and other real-life constraints related to time, distances and fleet. Other models considering demand uncertainty are the ones developed by Sumalee et al. [31] and Chu et al. [32], where the actual demand is revealed at the customer location and sometimes cannot be met, so that the vehicles have to return to the depot for replenishment. These types of models are also known as VRP with split deliveries [33]. Another variant of the VRP, quite common in last-mile logistics, is the one where pick-up and delivery happen both at the depot and at the customer location [34]. Pick-up and deliveries can also be simultaneous, i.e. it is served with a single stop by the supplier [35] or through cross-dock facilities or intermediate depots [36]. In particular, last-mile logistics have increased the interest towards outsourcing and split deliveries [37; 38], with the birth of VRP with outsourcing, in which a customer can be served using the own facilities and fleet, or by an external (outsourced) carrier.

Last-mile logistics usually needs an heterogeneous fleet; the Heterogeneous VRP (HVRP) [39] assumes that a mixed fleet of vehicles, having distinct capacities, fixed costs and travel costs, are used to serve a set of customers, minimizing the total costs or VRP with load-specific capacity [40] which can only accommodate one or more specific loads (e.g., multi-compartment vehicles where each compartment is dedicated to a specific type of freight). More recently, variants of the HVRP that incorporate these greener vehicles have been studied [41; 42].

The stochastic VRP (SVRP) is a variant of the VRP where one or more parameters are stochastic, i.e. it incorporates uncertainty in some parameters whose value is not known using random variables with a known probability distribution [43]. This means that routes cannot always be followed as planned and the solution cost must be minimized taking into account an expected value. Among SVRP we can find VRP with stochastic demand, VRP with stochastic customers, VRP with stochastic demands and customers, and VRP with stochastic travel and service times [43; 44; 45; 46].

The dynamic routing of vehicles comes into play in different situations occurring in last-mile logistics (e.g. vehicle's accidents, re-scheduling) and it may reduce operational costs, environmental impact and improve customer satisfaction. The family of problems called Dynamic VRP (DVRP) takes into account the time factor, i.e. variations in services and travel times [47] and travel time is a dynamic component of most real-world applications [47; 49]. The most common issue in DVRP are the online customer requests during the operation; the DVRP models are gaining popularity due to their ability to model just-in-time supply systems and to the diffusion of recent technological advancements, such as mobile devices or sensors, that allow drivers to dynamically change their routing [49]. An interesting example is the emergence of new customers at an unknown location when the vehicles are already on route; the objective in this case is to maximize the probability that these additional customers can be served without violating time constraints [49]. A dynamism in service times is commonly related to the variation in demand [50], but it can also be attributed to the availability of resources in customer premises [51]. A very recent similar issue in last-mile logistics is the one related to delivery or pick up of small parcels in the so-called parcel locker system; examples of these types of problems can be found in Grabenschweiger et al. [52] and Orenstein et al. [53].

When solving VRP in real-world last-mile logistics, there are several objective or performance measures which are often conflicting; in some sectors, (e.g. delivery of perishable foods) customer satisfaction and timely delivery is more important than minimizing

the distance travelled. Multi-Objective VRP (MOVRP) deals with these real-life instances [54; 55]. Examples of performance measures can be the driver workload, customer satisfaction, GHG emissions, etc. [56; 57]. An important difference with the classic VRP is that this family of problems has several optimal solutions, i.e. a set of non-dominated solutions called Pareto set or Pareto front [58]. The Pareto front is a set of non-dominated solutions, which fulfil the Pareto optimality property, i.e. no individual objective can be better off without making at least one individual objective worse. Examples of objectives used in the MOVRP are [59]: tour related, expressed in terms of total travel distance, the number of customers visited and time needed [55; 60; 58]; resource related, with both economic and sustainability meaning [61; 62]; node/arc related, which imply the minimization of the violated time window constraints [63; 64].

The class of algorithms used to solve the VRP variants varies with their degree of realism [28; 65; 66]. The classical VRP and all the subvariants are NP-hard, i.e. there is no deterministic algorithm that ensures to find the optimal solution for big size instances.

Several authors [67; 68] used Branch-and-cut method to solve VRPs; more in detail [69] defined set partitioning formulations that are exact methods to solve VRPs, associating a binary variable with each feasible route to search for optimal solutions. Another simple algorithm used to solve TSP and VRPs is 2-opt, which takes a route that crosses over itself and reorders the sequence of nodes so that it avoids the crossing, comparing every possible valid combination of the swapping mechanism [67].

Metaheuristics are among the most efficient approaches for VRPs, and they are strongly used in large-scale real-life applications. Examples of the use of metaheuristics in VRP problems are reported in the following. Simulated Annealing (SA) is often used when the search space is discrete (e.g., all tours that visit a given set of cities). Variable Neighbourhood Search is used when a change of the neighborhood structure is needed within the search, to find a local minimum [66; 49]. In the Ant colony optimization (ACO), a population-based metaheuristic, agents build solutions by moving on a graph-based representation of the problem, with a probabilistic model [70]. One of the metaheuristics most commonly implemented in software libraries for VRP is the Large Neighbourhood Search (LNS), in which the neighborhood of a solution is built by “destroying and repairing” part of the solution (usually with a randomness component); the opportunity to enlarge the neighbourhoods to be visited made this method very popular in VRPs solving [71; 72; 33; 12].

More recently hybrid metaheuristics have emerged as efficient methods to solve VRP problems and complex variants [73; 66]; hybridization can be performed with metaheuristics or with other operational research or artificial intelligence techniques. Several authors used hybrid metaheuristics to solve VRP problems. In their study [74] proposed a hybrid of metaheuristics combining Simulated Annealing and Tabu Search; the resulting effect is to allow movement in the solution space which results in increasing objective function. Vidal et al. [75] combined genetic search metaheuristic with three components of assignment, sequencing and route evaluation. Cattaruzza et al. [57] presented a route decomposition technique for chromosome decoding and a local search, to solve the multi-trip VRP with time windows and release dates. Liu et al. [76] proposed an iteration of Particle Swarm algorithm and Large Neighbourhood Search to escape from local optima. Avci et al. [77] developed a hybrid local search algorithm in which a non-monotone threshold adjusting strategy is integrated with tabu search. Jabir et al [78] used Ant Colony optimization (ACO) integrated with Variable Neighbourhood Search for solving large scale instances and proposed Integer Linear Programming models for a multi-depot vehicle routing problem. Later in 2018 Liu et al. [79] presented the hybridization of Ant Colony Optimization and Tabu Search; Ant Colony Optimization is used to search for a globally promising area, and then Tabu Search continues to optimize it to obtain a high-quality solution, with the initial solution of Tabu Search is provided by the final solution of Ant Colony Optimization. In 2019 Hosseinabadi et al. [80] proposed a hybridization of Gravitational Emulation Local Search and Genetic Algorithm (GA) using three standard

benchmarks found in the literature, and comparing the results with other metaheuristic algorithms, with competitive results. Lin et al. [81] created an initialization algorithm solution that combines a genetic algorithm with random components; they propose a specific crossover operator that generates feasible solutions, checks the constraints of the problem and integrates with a neighbourhood search heuristic.

3.3.3. Mixed approaches

A particular mention is deserved by the class of hybrid algorithms which combine metaheuristics with operational research or artificial intelligence methods. Yet in 2009, Kheirkhahzadeh and Barforoush [82] combined a hybrid ACO algorithm for solving vehicle routing problems heuristically with an exact algorithm to improve both the performance and the quality of solutions. Euchi et al. [83] developed and Artificial Ant Colony based on the 2-opt to solve dynamic pickup and delivery VRP; the success of this combinations is due to the intelligent exploitation of the problem structure and in an effective interplay between the search space and the solution space elaborating with the local search. More recently Gutierrez-Rodríguez et al. [84] presented a method to solve VRPs with time windows, based on selecting meta-heuristics via meta-learning, using a multi-layer perceptron classifier for the prediction task; experimental results show that this approach can effectively predict the best meta-heuristics for each problem type.

3.4. Discussion

Of the 78 papers analysed, 19 belong to the cluster of Machine Learning models, 56 to the one related to Vehicle Routing Optimization Models and 3 propose mixed approaches. This is mainly due to the novelty of the ML approaches. More in detail, all the papers belonging to the ML cluster and to the mixed cluster can be classified as research articles, while 17 studies of the VRO cluster can be classified as review papers.

A schematization of the papers belonging to the ML cluster can be found in Table 2. In particular, it is interesting to see that the main problems analysed through ML techniques are related to Anomaly Detection, Forecasting and Planning. The studies mainly adopt supervised learning techniques, while only Tamayo et al. [15] and Tian et al. [16] adopt unsupervised algorithms; the case studies treated are varied and this might be due to the novelty of the approach. There is not always a verification of the accuracy of the algorithm which is essential as it justifies the relationship between variables of the input data. Low accuracy is often due to the lack of additional data, unwanted presences of outliers in the training samples or wrong selection of features. Industrial AI applications today yield accuracy values of 99% and above to meet especially high safety demands.

Table 3 shows the articles belonging to the VRO cluster. The methods used are mostly metaheuristics, often of own elaboration, or well-known optimization algorithms, in particular PSO, ACO, LNS, MIP and GA. Case studies are mainly the synthetic ones usually analysed in the traditional literature on VRP; . Innovative use of algorithms or own approaches are often compared with the existing ones, to verify their effectiveness.

The three articles proposing hybrid approaches [83; 84; 82] all deal with variants of the VRP problem analysing synthetic case studies.

Finally, as already mentioned, the 17 review papers all deal with the topic of VRP. While some articles provide an overview on the generic approach [28; 29; 66; 26; 27], others deal with specific problems. Examples are those of Baldacci et al. [67], who analyse the variant of VRP under capacity and time window constraints, Costa et al. [68] who focus on branch-price-and-cut algorithms and Jozefowicz et al. [54] focusing on MOVRP. Literature on the DVRP is reviewed by Pillac et al. [47] and Psaraftis et al. [48], while SVRP is the core of the overviews conducted by Berhan et al. [43] and Oyola et al. [45; 46]; finally, [65] Caceres-Cruz et al., [73] Goel et al. and [30] Lahyani et al. conduct a deep analysis of RVRP studies.

Table 3. Articles belonging to the ML cluster

Problem	Author	Method/Algorithm	Case Study	Efficiency highlights
Anomaly Detection	Feng & Timmermans, 2015	Bayesian belief network, Decision Tree, RF	Trip purposes by GPS traces	Accuracy >96%
	Rosen & Medvedev, 2012	Own elaboration	Trajectories of freight ships	-
	Sarikan & Ozbayoglu, 2018	K-nearest neighbour	Vehicular flow directions	reliable in the case of a single lane road
	Savic et al., 2021 Sindhvani et al., 2020	Deep Learning Own elaboration	Container-carrying vehicles Drones flight	autoencoders are adequate for IoT successfully filter out anomalies from the training set
Classification Tasks	Lickert et al., 2021	Supervised Learning	Reverse Logistics	-
Demand Forecasting	Gao and Feng, 2009	SVM and Radial Basis Function Neural Network	Synthetic	SVM has higher stability
	Hess et al., 2021 Wojtusiak et al., 2012	RF and Support Vector Regression Inferential Theory of Learning	Urban delivery platform Autonomous logistics	Min accuracy>70% -
Entity matching	Bricher and Müller, 2020	Deep neural network	Container labelling	-
	Guermazi et al., 2020	Word Embedding and Supervised Learning	Validate logistics entities	-
Forecasting	Albadrani et al., 2021	K-nearest neighbours, RF, SVM	Inbound logistics	Accuracy >96%
	Kretschmar et al., 2016	Own elaboration	E-vehicles	-
Multicriteria analysis	Tian et al., 2021	Long Short-Term Memory	Customer satisfaction	blockchain into sustainability in urban logistics
Planning	Knoll et al., 2016	Framework	Inbound logistics	-
	Marcucci et al., 2020	Framework	Digital Twins	-
	Ouadi et al., 2020	Hybrid ML	Dimensioning of UCC	Close to 100%
Risk analysis	Zhao et al., 2020	GRNN, PSO	Safe operation of urban logistics	Accuracy = 80%
Sentiment analysis	Tamayo et al., 2020	Unsupervised Learning, Natural Language Processing	Opinions on city logistics	Positive feelings

Table 4. Articles belonging to the VRO cluster

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Problem	Author	Method/Algorithm	Case Study	Efficiency highlights
Capacitated VRP	Hosseinabadi et al., 2019	Gravitational Emulation Local Search and GA	Synthetic	Competitive with existing algorithms
DVRP	Grabenschweiger et al., 2021	Own elaboration	Parcel locker	-
	Liu et al., 2019	stochastic predictive control	Demand uncertainty	small up to medium scale real-world routing problems
	Okulewicz & Mańdziuk, 2019	PSO and Differential Evolution (DE), discrete encoding utilizing GA	Demand uncertainty	Both PSO and DE outperform GA
	Orenstein et al., 2019	savings heuristic, petal method and tabu search	Parcel locker	Outperforms existing algorithms
	Yan et al., 2019	MIP and dynamic neighbourhood search	Variation in supply	-
MOVRP	Cattaruzza et al., 2016	Hybrid metaheuristics	City Distribution Centres	Competitive with existing algorithms
	Cattaruzza et al., 2014	memetic algorithm	Synthetic	Outperforms existing algorithms
	Ganji et al., 2020	PSO, Non-dominated Sorting GA II, and ACO	Supply chain scheduling	NSGAI outperforms PSO and ACO
	Hassanzadeh & Rasti-Barzoki, 2017	Own elaboration	Supply chain scheduling	Outperforms other algorithms
	Qin et al., 2019	Own elaboration	Cold Chain Logistics	-
	Sivaram Kumar et al., 2018	Fitness Aggregated Genetic Algorithm (FAGA)	Synthetic	-
	Wang et al., 2016	multiobjective local search (MOLS) and multiobjective memetic algorithm (MOMA)	Reverse Logistics	MOLS outperforms MOMA
	Wang et al., 2020	Own elaboration	Synthetic	Outperforms existing algorithms
	Zhang et al., 2019	ACO	Synthetic and real case (food distribution logistics)	Competitive with existing algorithms
Periodic inventory RP	Liu et al., 2016	PSO and LNS	Synthetic	Outperforms existing algorithms

RVRP	Alcaraz et al., 2019	Own elaboration	Synthetic	-
	Ancele et al., 2021	SA	Synthetic	-
	Chu et al., 2017	two-stage heuristic solution	Demand uncertainty	-
	Gu et al., 2019	LNS	Split deliveries	Competitive with existing algorithms solving both small and large scale problem instances in reasonable amount of time
	Jabir et al., 2017	ACO, Variable Neighbourhood Search and Integer Linear Programming	Multi-depot	
	Sumalee et al., 2011	stochastic multi-modal network model	Demand uncertainty	-
SVRP	Bernardo et al., 2018	sampling strategies	Synthetic	-
Two-echelon VRP	Caggiani et al., 2021	MILP model	Use of green modes	-
	Grangier, et al., 2016	LNS	Synthetic	-
VRP	Andelmin & Bartolini, 2017	Own elaboration	Synthetic	instances with up to ~110 customers
	Avci et al., 2016	Hybrid metaheuristics	Reverse Logistics	Competitive with existing algorithms
	Baller et al., 2020	Own elaboration	Synthetic	-
	Ghilas et al., 2016	LNS	Pickup and Delivery with Time Windows	high-quality routing solutions for relatively large instances in a reasonable amount of time
	Lagos et al., 2018	PSO	Reverse Logistics	Competitive with existing algorithms
	Lin et al., 2009	SA and Tabu Search	Synthetic	Competitive with existing algorithms
	Lin et al., 2019	Hybrid metaheuristics	Synthetic	-
	Liu et al., 2018	ACO and Tabu Search	Cold-chain products (compatibility constraints)	instances with up to 80 customers and 10 good types
	Mavrovouniotis & Yang, 2015	ACO	Synthetic	immigrants schemes improve the performance of ACO
	Sivaram Kumar et al., 2014	Fitness Aggregated Genetic Algorithm (FAGA)	Synthetic	Competitive with existing algorithms
	Vidal et al., 2015	Hybrid metaheuristics	Synthetic	pre-processing phase may become time consuming for instances with large clusters

4. Conclusions

In recent years we have been witnessing an increase in the phenomenon of urban logistics, mainly due to the digitization of purchases and the consequent increase in online sales. However, last-mile logistics brings with it various externalities, and scholars and companies are always looking for solutions to improve their efficiency, both by relying on traditional methods and by resorting to recently developed methodologies, linked to artificial intelligence. This study offers an overview of the main scientific approaches proposed by scholars in recent years for improving the performance of urban logistics, focusing on the one hand on traditional techniques related to operational research, and on the other on new methodologies related to machine learning.

The results of the review of the main published and indexed articles show an increase in research in the sector in the last few years. In particular, the main techniques used in the case of ML approaches include supervised learning, with a variety of case studies analyzed. Particular attention is paid to the problems of demand forecasting and anomaly detection. The analysis paves the way for the development and testing of innovative unsupervised learning techniques for last-mile logistics.

The classic optimization techniques linked to operational research focus on VRP and its variants with particular attention to the issues of demand forecasting, reverse logistics, and multimodal fleet. Moreover, the review shows that new models have been developed that adapt the classic models to real problems and that most of the case studies focus on urban last-mile logistics. It can be seen that due to high customer demand and the need to improve environmental quality in cities, there is a tendency to create collaborative models between logistics operators, which is one of the main challenges in last-mile logistics today.

In summary, the analysis conducted can help to identify the best methods and algorithm to be applied for each problem and case study and can serve as a basis for future studies aiming at developing innovative solutions in last-mile logistics.

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